

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

I introduce with great pleasure the fourth regular issues of 2020. I'd like to thank all authors for contributing their sound research and the editorial board for the highly valuable review effort and comments for improvements. Furthermore, I'd like to particularly thank our consortium members for their generous financial support and the J.UCS team for their great organizational support.

As always, we are also interested in high quality proposals of special issues covering emerging topics and new trends in computer science. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles to our journal.

Since we further want to extend our editorial board, please apply for a membership in our editorial board if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record.

In this regular issue, I am very happy to introduce 4 accepted regular papers from 4 different countries.

In their collaborative research between Brazil and Spain, Ana Paula Allian, Edson Oliveira Jr, Rafael Capilla, and Elisa Yumi Nakagawa investigate how existing software variability tools fulfill the needs of companies. José Eduardo de Almeida Ayres and Luiz Henrique de Figueiredo from Brazil cover in their research the development of rigorous numerical methods based on interval analysis for finding all fixed points of a map and all attracting periodic points of a complex polynomial. Xia He, Guoping Du, and Long Hong from China introduce a formal extension language of judgments for distinguishing universal judgments and particular judgments. Jisha Maniamma and Hiroaki Wagatsuma from Japan introduce their work on a semantic web-based representation of human-logical inference for solving Bongard problems.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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